

STRUCTURAL QUALITY BIOCOMPOSITES OF TREATED FLAX FIBER WITH EPOXIDIZED SUCROSE SOYATE RESIN

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1 General Introduction

Looming scarcity of sources for petrochemical-based materials, as well as the associated high costs, has spurred interest in renewable sources for use in functional and structural materials. A major hurdle to this aspiration is the necessity of maintaining the properties delivered by petrochemical based materials while replacing them with biobased analogs.

To date, little success has been seen in efforts to achieve composites having the properties required of structural applications through the incorporation of biobased fibers and fillers into purely biobased resins. As a general rule, achieving high levels of performance has required extensive modification and dilution of the biobased resin. For instance, the

addition of acrylate groups to epoxidized soybean oil (ESO) is a frequently employed method of improving its properties [1]. This acrylated ESO is then usually further blended with up to 35 wt% petrochemical based monomers such as styrene [2]. Additional modifications that have been employed include hydroxylation, maleinization, and phthalation [3]. While the final products of such efforts are resins of acceptable properties, these strategies also result in significant dilution of their renewable content. The number of steps required to accomplish such modest gains in renewability likely prompts many to raise questions as to the practicality of such efforts.

In contrast to resins obtained through the modification and dilution strategies outlined above, a new biobased thermosetting matrix resin,

Fig. 1. Derivation of ESS from soybean oil and sucrose.

epoxidized sucrose soyate (ESS), in conjunction with surface treated flax fiber, shows the potential for overcoming the current performance limitations of significantly biobased composites.

For the purposes of this study, properties commonly achieved by fiberglass composites were adopted as benchmarks by which the performance of the samples produced in this study can be judged. These standards are 200-225 MPa for tensile and flexural strength, 16-18 GPa for tensile modulus, 11-13 GPa for flexural modulus, and 25-30 MPa for interlaminar shear strength. Indications suggest the likelihood of developing structural quality composites of ESS and treated flax fiber having biocontent in excess of 80%.

2 A Truly High-Biocontent Biocomposite

2.1 Biobased Resin Matrix

Derived from sugar and soybean oil, ESS is an entirely biobased material. The precursor, sucrose soyate (SS), is produced via a transesterification reaction of soybean oil and sucrose. As a result of this reaction, the long chain fatty acids of soybean oil are transferred to sucrose molecules at the locations of sucrose's eight hydroxyl groups. Epoxidation of SS is accomplished via treatment with acetic acid and hydrogen peroxide in conjunction with an acidic ion-exchange resin catalyst. The resulting in situ-generated peracetic

acid effects a nearly complete conversion (>99%) of double bonds to oxirane moieties [4], [5]. This process is illustrated in Figure 1.

ESS is light in color, and has a compact, highly functionalized molecular structure. Epoxy functionality for ESS ranges from 10 to 12 oxirane groups per molecule, compared to the 4.4 groups per molecule of traditional ESO. Initial trials have demonstrated its utility. It has the ability to be cured under a broad range of time and temperature conditions, it has low moisture absorption and good adhesion to a variety of substrates. It also exhibits highly competitive mechanical properties. For example, when ESS is crosslinked with a cycloaliphatic anhydride, the resulting tensile modulus values of 450-1000 MPa are in the range of current thermosetting polymer technology.

2.2 Natural Fiber Reinforcement

In addition to being renewable, natural fibers are characterized by a number of beneficial traits, making them well suited for use as substitutes for traditional glass fiber reinforcement. They are less abrasive to manufacturing machinery than glass, and pose little or no health risk to those working with them [6]. They are readily available and are biodegradable. Their low density translates into high specific properties such as modulus [7], flexibility [8], strength, stiffness [6], and impact resistance [9]. Natural fibers also exhibit superior vibration damping [9].

Table 1. Structural compositions of natural fibers [14], [15].

Fiber	Cellulose (wt.%)	Lignin (wt.%)	Hemicellulose (wt.%)	Pectin (wt.%)	Wax (wt.%)	Spiral angle (°)
Bast fibers						
Jute	61 - 71.5	12 - 13	13.6 - 20.4	0.2	0.5	8.0
Flax	71	2.2	18.6 - 20.6	2.3	1.7	10.0
Hemp	70.2 - 74.4	3.7 - 5.7	17.9 - 22.4	0.9	0.8	6.2
Ramie	68.6 - 76.2	0.6 - 0.7	13.1 - 16.7	1.9	0.3	7.5
Kenaf	31 - 39	15 - 19	21.5	-	-	-
Leaf fibers						
Sisal	67 - 78	8.0 - 11.0	10.0 - 14.2	10.0	2.0	20.0
Pineapple	70 - 82	5 - 12	-	-	-	14.0
Henequen	77.6	13.1	4 - 8	-	-	-
Seed fibers						
Cotton	82.7	0.7 - 1.6	5.7	-	0.6	

In addition to the positive traits mentioned above, there are several less desirable characteristics of natural fibers that require cognizance. The properties of vegetable based natural fibers vary with such factors as growing season, region of origin, fiber age, storage environment, and processing methods [10]. Low degradation temperatures limit processing and service temperatures to below 200 °C [6]. Natural fibers also have a hydrophilic nature, which results in a tendency toward high moisture absorption and, perhaps their most detrimental aspect, a poor ability to adhere to non-polar, more hydrophobic polymer matrix materials. Fortunately this poor matrix compatibility can be palliated through any of several relatively simple fiber pre-treatments. Mercerization, which is treatment in an alkali solution, is certainly one of the most popular. This process alters the surface chemistry of the fiber, increasing the number of active hydroxyl groups. An added benefit of this treatment is that it strips away much of the non-cellulose material of the fiber, effectively increasing its relative cellulose content [11]. This further increases its already laudable specific strength.

Natural fibers originating from plants can be grouped into three categories: leaf, seed/fruit, and bast (stem) fibers [12], [13]. In general, these fibers consist of similar constituents, though often in varying combinations and configurations. Table 1 lists the makeup of several common natural fibers [14], [15]. The most critical of the components is cellulose, which provides the majority of a fiber's strength. Cellulose makes up anywhere from 61% to 83% of the fibers included in the table. In addition to cellulose, other components include hemicellulose, lignin, pectin and various waxes [16]. Each of these materials has its own characteristic mechanical properties which contribute to the overall properties of the fiber that incorporates them. As such, natural fibers can rightly be considered composites in and of themselves. Just as orientation of the fibers in a conventional composite influence the composite's properties, so too does the microfibrillar angle impact the properties of natural fibers. Specifically, low microfibrillar angles equate to higher strength fibers [17].

Bast fibers come from the phloem, or nutrient-conducting tissue of a plant. This category includes

such fibers as banana, flax, hemp, jute, kenaf, mesta, ramie, and rattan [18], [19]. As may be expected, based on the part of the plant from which they are obtained, bast fibers are among the longest natural fibers available. Not as obvious, perhaps, is that they also include some of the strongest natural fibers available. As a result, bast fibers are often a first choice when composites with optimal strength are desired. Among the readily available natural fibers, flax has the greatest modulus of elasticity and tensile strength due, in part, to its high cellulose content [20].

Recently, flax fiber has been prepared for incorporation into ESS resin using varied treatments. Both loose flax fiber and unidirectional flax fabric were treated in 0.25 molar solutions of NaOH in 95% ethanol (5% water). Additionally, some loose fiber was treated in a solution of 0.25 moles of NaOH dissolved in 10% ethanol (90% water). In both cases, this treatment consisted of immersing the fiber in the boiling NaOH solution in quantities of approximately 1g fiber per 13.3 mL of solution. Following two hours of treatment, the solution was decanted off and the fiber carefully rinsed in water until the rinse water no longer acquired a brown color when the fiber was gently agitated. The washed fiber was straightened when necessary and laid flat to dry. It was then placed in an oven to dry at 80 °C for 24 hours. In the case of loose fiber, after drying, the fiber was then carefully separated and straightened.

In addition to treatment in NaOH solution, a quantity of mercerized unidirectional fabric was then treated in a 20 wt% solution of 4-methyl-1,2-cyclohexanedicarboxylic anhydride (MHHPA) crosslinker in acetone for an hour and a half. It was then triple rinsed in acetone, straightened as necessary, and placed on a tray to dry in an oven at 80 °C for 24 hours.

2.3 Composite Manufacture

2.3.1 Loose Fiber Composite Manufacture

Loose flax fiber has been incorporated into small volume biocomposite coupons with fiber loadings of up to 55% using a modified vacuum assisted resin transfer molding (VARTM) process. These coupons incorporated flax fiber in either a treated or untreated state, as well as one of two different formulations of ESS crosslinked with MHHPA in the presence of 1,8-diazabicyclo[5.4.0]undec-7-ene

(DBU) as a catalyst. Coupons of untreated flax and a commercially available petrochemical based epoxy resin (Araldite 8601/Aradur 8602) were produced as a source of baseline data. For further comparison purposes, coupons of glass fiber and this commercially available resin, as well as coupons of the two ESS formulations were manufactured.

Considerable care was required in the layup of the loose fiber in order to obtain a final product with some semblance of unidirectionality. Even so, the resulting composites were characterized by noticeably wavy fiber. In each case, a glass plate which had been treated with release agent was used as a tool surface. On this plate, approximately 60 g of fiber was spread evenly in a slightly oversized approximation of the desired dimensions of the resulting composite. A release agent-coated caul plate was placed atop the fiber to ensure the resulting composite had both a uniform cross section and smooth surfaces. The layup was then sealed under bagging film and exposed to a vacuum of 24 in Hg for at least two hours in an effort to remove residual moisture, volatiles, and as much air as possible from the fiber.

ESS formulation one (ESS F1) was prepared using an epoxide / anhydride molar ratio of 1 / 0.5. ESS formulation two (ESS F2) was prepared using an epoxide / anhydride molar ratio of 1 / 0.75. In both cases, the amount of DBU used was 1.5 wt% of the combined weight of ESS and MHPA. The Araldite resin was mixed at a 4/1 ratio of resin to hardener, as prescribed by the manufacturer.

Prior to infusion, the ESS resins were warmed to 50 °C, and the press platens and fiber layup were pre-heated to 60 °C. Prior to infusion of the Araldite resin, it was placed in a vacuum chamber and degassed under a vacuum of 24 in Hg for five minutes.

During infusion of the ESS resins, the temperature setting on the platens was increased to 90 °C once the infusion was 75% complete.

Following infusion, the inlet hose was clamped and an external pressure of 2.5 metric tons was slowly applied. Once the excess resin was drawn through the outlet hose, it was clamped off also. In the case of the ESS resins, the temperature of the platens was set to 120 °C.

Once the temperature of the platens reached their set point of 120 °C, the ESS composites were allowed to cure for two hours. After this time, the panel was removed from the press and separated from the glass tool plate to allow for even cooling. The Araldite panels were allowed to cure in the press overnight before being removed from the press.

2.3.2 Unidirectional Fabric Composite Manufacture

Unidirectional flax fabric has also been incorporated into small volume biocomposite coupons with fiber loadings of up to 55% using the same modified VARTM process described above. These coupons incorporated the virgin, mercerized, or MHPA-treated flax fabric whose preparation was described above. In addition, these coupons utilized one of the three resins mentioned above (ESS F1, ESS F2, and Araldite 8601/Aradur 8602).

For each composite, 12 sheets of fabric having dimensions slightly greater than that desired of the intended coupon were stacked on a release agent-treated glass plate. The total mass of the fabric used in each coupon was approximately 75 g. A release agent-coated caul plate was placed atop the fiber to ensure the resulting composite had both a uniform cross section and smooth surfaces. The layup was then sealed under bagging film and exposed to a vacuum of 24 in Hg for at least two hours in an effort to remove residual moisture, volatiles, and as

Table 2. Mechanical properties of 50 Vol. % loose flax fiber/ Araldite, ESS reinforcements in longitudinal direction.

Category	Untreated Fiber			NaOH Treated Fiber	
	Araldite	ESS F1	ESS F2	Araldite	ESS F2
Tens. Str. MPa	158.09 ± 21.69	154.16 ± 6.77	152.58 ± 15.99	NA	178.31 ± 38.93
Flex. Str. MPa	195.65 ± 24.64	252.42 ± 24.20	340.30 ± 28.17	242.00 ± 22.5	259.45 ± 12.36
Sht. Beam Str. MPa	12.65 ± 1.56	22.32 ± 3.16	25.63 ± 2.46	23.32 ± 0.25	25.35 ± 1.76

much air as possible from the fiber.

ESS formulation one (ESS F1) was prepared using an epoxide / anhydride molar ratio of 1 / 0.5. ESS formulation two (ESS F2) was prepared using an epoxide / anhydride molar ratio of 1 / 0.75. In both cases, the amount of DBU used was 1.5 wt% of the combined weight of ESS and MHHPA. The Araldite resin was mixed at a 4/1 ratio of resin to hardener, as prescribed by the manufacturer.

Prior to infusion, the ESS resins were warmed to 50 °C, and the press platens and fiber layup were pre-heated to 60 °C. Prior to infusion of the Araldite resin, it was placed in a vacuum chamber and degassed under a vacuum of 24 in Hg for five minutes.

During infusion of the ESS resins, the temperature setting on the platens was increased to 90 °C once the infusion was 75% complete.

Following infusion, the inlet hose was clamped and an external pressure of 4.5 metric tons was slowly applied. Once the excess resin was drawn through the outlet hose, it was clamped off also. In the case of the ESS resins, the temperature of the platens was set to 120 °C.

Once the temperature of the platens reached their set point of 120 °C, the ESS composites were allowed to cure for two hours. After this time, the panel was removed from the press and separated from the glass tool plate to allow for even cooling. The Araldite panels were allowed to cure in the press overnight before being removed from the press.

2.4 Composite Properties

Mechanical testing of properties such as density, tensile strength (ASTM D3039), flexural strength (ASTM D790), and interlaminar shear strength (ASTM D2344) have been carried out on both the samples prepared using loose fiber, as well as those prepared using unidirectional fabric. Results were normalized to a fiber volume fraction (V_f) of 50%.

2.4.1 Loose Fiber Composite

Predictably, there was little difference in the tensile strengths of composites of similar fiber type and treatment. As shown in Table 2, however, a marked increase in tensile strength was seen in NaOH treated fiber over untreated fiber for ESS F2. In addition, in the areas of flexural and interlaminar

shear strength, the commercially available resin was consistently the poorest performer. When measured, ESS F2 was consistently the best performer with properties approaching and exceeding twice those of the commercially available resin. ESS F1 was either statistically equivalent to, or superior to, the commercially available resin.

The loose fiber composites produced using the techniques and materials described above achieve a tensile strength that is 70% of the minimum target property, tensile modulus that is 280% that of the minimum target, and 92% of the minimum desired interlaminar shear strength. However, it should be noted that the significant waviness of the loose fiber should be expected to produce composites of lower properties than would be observed if the fibers were straight. Additionally, the randomness of the fiber waviness renders impossible any effort to quantify the magnitude of the resulting property deficit. What can be said is that, should improved processing methods result in composites of straighter fiber, their properties can be expected to be greater than those obtained here.

2.4.2 Unidirectional Fabric Composite

As with the loose fiber composites, those of unidirectional fabric exhibited relatively little variation in tensile strengths. As can be seen in Figure 2, all other panels approach or exceed the target of 200 - 225 MPa tensile strength.

In the case of flexural strength, ESS F2 is superior to Araldite, which is superior to ESS F1. In addition, there also appears to be a progressive improvement in properties with the extent of fiber treatment. The best performance was demonstrated by MHHPA ESS F2, which exhibited a flexural strength exceeding 250 MPa, which exceeds the goal by 25 MPa.

In the area of interlaminar shear strength, a similar pattern of ESS F2 outperforming Araldite which outperforms ESS F1 emerges. However, in the area of fiber treatment, NaOH treated fiber appears to be superior to MHHPA treated fiber, while untreated fiber remains the least effective. The MHHPA F2 and NaOH Araldite composites were found to reach or exceed the top end of the desired 25 to 30 MPa range.

Fig 2. Mechanical properties normalized to 50% V_f.

Results for tensile modulus do not show statistically significant variation between the coupons. However, the trend for ESS F1 resin to produce the poorest results appears to be true in this case as well. Even so, all coupons greatly exceeded the goal of 16 to 18 GPa.

Flexural modulus results again show that ESS F1 performs more poorly than the other two resins. Also, it appears that there is little or no statistically significant variation between fiber treatment. It would appear that a flexural modulus of 18 GPa should be achievable on a consistent basis, which greatly exceeds the goal of 11-13 GPa.

3 Biocontent

The fiber and resin components of the composites produced are substantially biobased. ESS resin itself is 100% biobased, while the MHPA and DBU are entirely petrochemical-based. Untreated and NaOH treated flax fiber is entirely biobased. A small percentage of the MHPA treated fiber's weight is not biobased, however a definitive quantification of this percentage has not yet been established. For the purpose of discussion, it is assumed that a generous 5% of the total weight of these fibers is non-biobased. The renewable portion of the resulting composites is presented in Figure 3. Biocontent of nearly 90% has been achieved using ESS F1.

4 Further Discussion and Conclusions

At the outset of this study, the assumption was that this new resin system would provide a significant improvement over current biobased technology, but would still require a modicum of glass fiber in order

to achieve structural quality properties. However, in light of the properties demonstrated by the unidirectional fiber composites, it would appear that supplementing with glass fiber in order to reach the benchmark is not necessary. In all areas, the benchmarks were met or exceeded without the incorporation of glass fiber.

Results obtained from composites of loose fiber, as well as those panels consisting of poorly aligned fabric, underscore the fact that good fiber alignment is essential. This speaks to the fact that refinements in fiber treatment and manufacturing techniques play a major role in the successful fabrication of structural quality biocomposites.

While the results show that composites manufactured using unidirectional fabric performed better than those of loose fiber, the smallest gain was seen in the area of interlaminar shear strength. In fact, significant difficulty was experienced in successfully obtaining shear failure during testing of loose fiber samples. As a result, the actual shear strengths of these composites may be greater than those reported here, and the difference in performance between the two composite types may be even smaller than reported. The non-laminar, three dimensional quality of the loose fiber is quite likely the reason for the relatively good performance of loose fiber in this area when compared to the stratified fabric-based composite.

There are several notable differences between the loose and unidirectional flax fibers used in this study. The unidirectional fiber incorporates yarns of twisted fibers which are approximately two inches in length. These fibers are sized with a wheat starch. The loose flax is not twisted. For the most part, the length of individual fibers spans that of the composite coupons. It also has no sizing applied to it. The sizing on the unidirectional fabric likely results some variation in the efficacy of the mercerization between the fiber types, though it is unknown how significant this effect is. Also, while unlikely to be economically viable in a production setting, should a method be devised by which loose fiber can be significantly straightened, it is likely that coupons incorporating loose fiber would demonstrate properties superior to those obtained using the unidirectional fabric for the following reasons: the process of manufacturing the unidirectional fabric inflicts significantly more damage on the individual fibers; there is a

Fig 3. Biocontent % of unidirectional flax composites.

significant length difference between the two fiber types; the twist of the fibers in the unidirectional fabric guarantees that all fibers are slightly off-axis. The amount of external pressure applied to infused fiber generally dictates the fiber fraction of the resulting composite. As a result, greater pressure results in greater properties to the extent that the pressure is not so great that there is no longer sufficient matrix to transfer load between fibers. The amount of pressure used in the manufacture of the unidirectional fabric composites has not been fully fine tuned. It is likely that the pressure used is not ideal. It is also possible that the optimum pressure varies with fiber treatment type.

5 Future Work

5.1 Additional Resin Formulation

Structure-property studies of the matrix resin system will be carried out to understand the impact of variables such as epoxy functionality, anhydride crosslinker, catalyst and loading, and curing conditions on properties such as modulus, impact resistance, glass transition temperature, thermal stability, water sorption, and durability.

5.2 Additional Fiber Treatment

It is expected that continual refinements to the techniques used in fiber treatment will further increase the cost effectiveness of the process, as well as the performance and biocontent of the resulting material.

5.3 Additional Composite Manufacture

Continuing refinements to the techniques used in composite manufacture are expected to further improve the cost effectiveness of the process, as well as increase the performance and biocontent of the resulting material.

As mentioned above, a systematic study of the external pressure applied to composites of varying fiber treatments would be beneficial and likely result in further property improvements.

In addition, in the interest of broadening the scope of this study and more fully understanding the performance and potential of this material, it is intended that future work will include the manufacture of ESS infused sandwich composites

incorporating randomly oriented fiber mat and a biobased polyurethane foam.

5.4 Additional Testing

It is intended that future tests will be conducted to determine the durability of the matrix resin. Similarly, structure-process-property relationships will be established for the biocomposites produced with regards to durability for use as a structural construction grade material. Microscopy studies will be carried out to examine fiber-matrix interactions.

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